

THE ANALYSIS OF THE STYLISTIC POTENTIAL OF TENSE-ASPECT VERBAL FORMS IN MODERN ENGLISH BY GEORGE YULE

<https://doi.org10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.6464578>

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Annotation: *More and more linguists and specialists in study of literature attract their attention to problems of Stylistics nowadays. But at the same time as well as in any other science we can see the integration of the processes that is the intensification of different parts of knowledge and appearance of new modern synthetic sections. Such as new problems have been involved in the sphere of stylistic researches, a lot of data and programs have been studied and new aspects of language factors and features have been discovered. Our interest in these points is George Yule's contribution to the field of stylistics.*

Key words: *grammar, philologist, denotation, stylistics, present, past, tense-aspect, lexical aspect, context.*

From the point of our view English Grammar is one of the most difficult subject for study not only for students but everyone who wants to be a professional philologist or linguist. The verb as a party of speech is the most capacious grammar category in English. In verbal word with all variety of its denotations, meanings and stylistic potentials there are combinations with different grammar forms, organic connections and associations with tenses and aspect, which characterize all verbal system in the whole [1;340]. The role of some scholars in development of Stylistics is very high especially in Stylistic Grammar but in the whole, not specifically: Palmer, Hornby, Quirk, Yule, Skrebnev, Block and others. In our days the interest in this problem increases because we can see some questions and problems which are not studied enough.

We have analyzed some works of G.Yule in this field. **George Yule** (born 20 March 1947) is a Scottish-American linguist. He is known for his works on [pragmatics](#) and [discourse analysis](#) . He now lives in [Hawai'i](#) . He studied at [Edinburgh University](#), completing an M.A. in English Language and Literature (1969), M.Sc. in Applied Linguistics (1978), and a PhD in Linguistics (1981). His best-known work is an introductory textbook about language [9] .

There are two important facts in relation to the notion of "tense". First, from a formal point of view, tense is a grammatical category, usually expressed overtly

on the verb. Second, from a semantic viewpoint, tense serves to locate situations in time. **George Yule's** classic work "**Explaining English Grammar**" describes and explains the basic forms of the present and past tenses, perfect and progressive aspects and main structures of the English verb complex as well. According to G. Yule's system [5; 54–84] in order to describe the different forms of a verb, we need to talk about **tense**, which often has to do with the location of a situation in time, and **aspect**, which characterizes the way in which that situation is perceived or experienced. The author affirms that English has two distinct tense forms, they are **present and past tenses**, and two distinct forms for aspect, **perfect and progressive aspects**, which are marked on the verb. G. Yule underlines that the sense of team «**tense**» in English is not based on simple distinctions in time: e.g.

And today you woke with splitting headache.

Tomorrow I fly to London for a big meeting.

Yesterday the land tells me my rent's going up.

The present form here ties the situation described closely to the situation of utterance. The past tense form makes the situation described more remote from the situation of utterance. Situation in the future are treated differently they are inherently non-factual. The author means that the verb form that is traditionally called «future tense» is actually expressed via a modal verb which indicates the relative possibility of the event. The author means that the verb form that is traditionally called «**future tense**» is actually expressed via a **modal verb** which indicates the relative possibility of the event. What is aspect?

Aspect is divided by author into two parts [5; 63–68]:

1. Lexical aspect (stative and dynamic verbs);

2. Grammatical:

– **progressive** viewed from the inside in progress;

– **perfect** viewed from outside in retrospect.

Tense is the location of a situation, aspect – the inside of a situation. In parts «**Meaning in Contexts**» [5; 68–72] Yule shows how to use the stylistic potential of tense and aspect in the practical approach.

When we construct a piece of connected speech or writing, whether in monologue or dialogue, we are constantly tapping the lexical and grammatical resources of English verb to find of making our composition and particular effect.

Describing how to use deferent styles in a magazine article, news reports, academic writing, narratives, spoken discuses and others Yule gives some easy explanations:

– information that is treated as part of the «**background**» will tend to be expressed in the **past tense**;

- information that is current concern, in the «**foreground**» will be expressed in the **present tense**;

- background scene-setting, particularly in stories, is often expressed in the **past progressive**;

- ongoing current situations are described in the **present progressive**;

- viewing recent changes from the current situation is typically expressed by **perfect aspect**.

Following the description of basic verbal forms, Yule conveys not only specific features of verbal forms and structures according to tenses and aspects, but includes a piece of information on how meanings of verbal forms can be shaped by context and communicative purpose - **stylistic potential of verbal forms**.

To conclude, tense – the position of the state or action in time, that is, whether it is in the past, present or future. Aspect – the extension of the state or action in time, that is, whether it is unitary (perfective), continuous or repeated (imperfective). The issue about the stylistic potential of tense-aspect verbal forms is still being analyzed by linguists all over the world.

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